

AXIOLOGICAL APPROACH TO PATRIOTIC EDUCATION.

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Annotation: *today it is an important issue to deeply immerse our national values in the consciousness of generation and thereby find a solution to feelings of confidence in the future in our beliefs. The soil of our country, no doubt, is considered the cradle of immortal values. Patriotic virtue is considered one of the most important aspects on the basis of national values.*

Keywords: *patriotism, state, process, development.*

A person does not remain selfless with the condemnation of patriotism. Today, every member of society feels the motherland with his heart, and the opportunity to reach the desired heights will increase even more if he can become a participant in the reforms carried out in our country as a recognized soul.

Educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is an issue for all of us that will never lose its relevance and importance. This urgent issue is a continuous process, which consists of a complex of interconnected political-legal, socio-economic, ideological-ideological, cultural-educational activities. Today, the work on educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotic is carried out in accordance with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees and resolutions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers, universal statutes of. The development of any state is determined by a number of objective and subjective factors, among which the development and adoption of a person acting in the rules, principles and laws of power, the fulfillment of the specific obligations of each citizen occupy a special place. This trend requires a detailed examination of the organization of the educational process; development and testing of alternative teaching models; ensuring the information security of the educational process undoubtedly, the formation of civic qualities in a person to some extent contributes to a change in priorities in the field of Education.

It includes the final goal of education and upbringing, changes in the worldview of the reader. The goal of the school is to educate a person who has a set of rights and duties guaranteed by the state, is Democratic, loyal to the ideas of social partnership, respects national and personal freedom for himself and others. The problems of patriotic education were expressed in

the works of thinkers and public figures of the past Navoi, Babir, Amir Temur, Ushinsky, Sukhomlinsky and others. They believed that the main goal of upbringing is to form a patriotic person who loves his people, language, culture, traditions, is highly spiritual, loving to science, hardworking, serving the motherland. Of great importance in achieving the goals of patriotic education is the spiritual and spiritual experience of previous generations.

Ensuring the continuity and continuity of the past with the present serves to preserve national and universal values, through which each nation reproduces its spiritual, ethnic psychology, traditions, customs and character. Because the historically formed high national values of our people help to overcome the challenges of the prosperity of society, such as patriotism, humanity, justice, spiritual exaltation of national pride.

First of all, information about Mahmoud Thorabi. He was a sieve - poor, Sheikh. He lived in the village of Torob, located about 20 kilometers from Bukhara. We will never exaggerate if we say that this baby belonging to the Jondor district has become the center of the fight against the oppression of Mughal invaders. Because in the dolgali years of the 13 century, the Mongols wanted and were often revolted by the local population against their oppression. The desire to see the land free and prosperous was the main parable of the elusive people like Mahmud Torobi.

Sources say that in 1238, the peasants and poor of the shu and the surrounding villages, in mutual consultation, enter into an open struggle against the invaders of the land. The agitators, under the leadership of Mahmoud Torabi, will take the city on a walk to Bukhara. Malik makes Sanjar Castle their residence.

Loyalty to the motherland, patriotism with its powerful roots goes back to a deep reverence for the honor of the family, generation-ancestors, a person's loyalty to his own conscience and duty. Only then does the younger generation strive to work in the interests of the motherland and the country, and, moreover, in a pure and conscientious way for tomorrow's future. We must teach our youth the mechanisms of establishing traditions and practices in universal, national, secular, moral, aesthetic, social, family, historical, religious, economic, spiritual, political ravages in the fight against the negative vices present in society, including corruption. In the system of teacher activities, the creation and implementation of a model for the formation of patriotic qualities of students in the pedagogical process gives an effective result. One of the directions of folk pedagogy in epics, such human ideas as goodness, freedom, patriotism, nationalism, heroism were

singled out with unparalleled skill and always led a person to spiritual perfection.

In the study of reality, along with other methods of scientific knowledge, the axiological approach is of great importance. In scientific cognition, it is extremely important to determine the universe, what is in it, event, phenomenon, etc., the reflection of value in the human mind, the laws of the perception of value in accordance with reality, the degree and possibility of determining its criteria. General knowledge of this theory along with axiology (gnoseology) is based on data from the social and natural sciences, especially on the physiology of the higher nervous system, sensory organs and evidence of mental activity, the achievements of such disciplines as logic, linguistics. Axiology is a philosophical doctrine, a process of historical development in the history of material, cultural, spiritual, axiological and psychological cadre of a person, community, society, their interaction with the world of values, changes in the cadre and regulatory system.

The understanding of values, the combination of emotional and mental knowledge in learning, the generalization of concepts, terms and signs of judgments, conclusions, the analysis of axiological processes in natural and social reality, the practical functioning of relying on them mean an inextricable process related to each other.

The study of this aspect of the issue relies on the evidence of moral science, aesthetics, jurisprudence, Cultural Studies, Political Science and the social aspects of the gloomy age. Of great importance in this is the determination of the value of economic, political, spiritual activities and processes for society and social entities, problems reflecting different aspects of life, as well as views, ideas, teachings, requirements and needs that represent their solutions for Real processes.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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